

DriftMoE: A Mixture of Experts Approach to Handle Concept Drifts

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PROBLEM & MOTIVATION

- Concept drift challenges
- On-stationary streams
- Resource constraints
- Current Limitations
 - False positive detection
 - Coarse adaptation
 - Simple voting schemes

SOLUTION OVERVIEW

- **DriftMoE Framework:**
 - Online MoE architecture
 - Co-training approach
 - Neural router + experts
- **Two Variants:**
 - MoE-Data (multi-class)
 - MoE-Task (one-vs-rest)

KEY FEATURES & ARCHITECTURE

- Multi-hot correctness
- Mask training
- Cooperative feedback
- Symbiotic learning
- Resource efficiency:
- Cooperative feedback 12 vs 100+ experts

- Technical Details:**
- Hoeffding Tree experts
 - BCE loss optimization
 - Online mini-batches

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Category	Stream	Instances	Features	Classes
Synthetic	LED (Abrupt)	1,000,000	24	10
	LED (Gradual)	1,000,000	24	10
	SEA (Abrupt)	1,000,000	3	2
	SEA (Gradual)	1,000,000	3	2
	RBF_m	1,000,000	10	5
	RBF_f	1,000,000	10	5
Real	Airlines	539,383	7	2
	Electricity	45,312	8	2
	Cover Type	581,012	54	7

- 9 benchmarks (6+3 real)
- Prequential evaluation
- 5 state-of-art baseline
- Accuracy, Kappa metrics

KEY FINDINGS

- Summary:**
- ✓ Competitive accuracy
 - ✓ 8x fewer resources
 - ✓ Fast drift adaptation

- Future Directions:**
- ✓ Uncertainty routing
 - ✓ Dynamic allocation
 - ✓ Cost-sensitive losses

RESULTS & PERFORMANCE

Table 1: DriftMoE Performance Summary

Dataset	MoEData	MoETask
Airlines	70.33 ± 0.18	60.92 ± 0.01
CovType	81.28 ± 0.75	58.28 ± 0.31
Electricity	83.76 ± 0.45	68.73 ± 0.85
LED _a	73.77 ± 0.18	71.11 ± 0.54
LED _g	73.11 ± 0.11	70.82 ± 0.38
RBF _f	61.90 ± 0.20	75.45 ± 0.11
RBF _m	79.89 ± 0.48	88.65 ± 0.07
SEA _a	89.09 ± 0.05	88.04 ± 0.09
SEA _g	88.74 ± 0.05	87.76 ± 0.04

CONCLUSIONS

- Main Contributions:**
- First streaming MoE for concept drift
 - Novel co-training framework
 - Multi-hot feedback
 - Competitive performance with fewer resources

- Impact:**
- Scalable online learning
 - Efficient drift handling

USE CASES

- Applications:**
- IoT data streams
 - Financial markets
 - Social media feeds
 - Edge computing
- Deployment:**
- Resource-constrained environments
 - Real-time inference
 - Adaptive edge devices
 - Streaming analytics

FUNDING

